

OBSERVATION ON THE RELATION BETWEEN PREGNANCY, SEX HORMONES AND THE VITAMIN C CONTENT OF THE TISSUES OF GUINEA-PIGS.

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The effect of pregnancy and of the injection of a luteinising hormone on the onset of scurvy in guinea-pigs was investigated and, contrary to Bourne, no delaying effect was observed. Injections of luteinising and follicular hormones into virgin guinea-pigs did not appreciably alter the vitamin C content of the different tissues of the animals. Results of statistical analysis are given.

It was claimed by Bourne (*Nature*, 1935, 135, 148) that injection of the hormone preparation antuitrin-S into female guinea-pigs fed on a scorbutic diet prevented or delayed the onset of scurvy. As antuitrin-S stimulates the corpus luteum of the ovary, it was supposed that the luteal tissue was capable of synthesising vitamin C. It was also shown by Mouriquand and Schoen (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1933, 107, 203) that gravid female guinea-pigs develop no or very slight scurvy when kept on a scorbutic diet. Further observations by Rohmer *et al* (*Nature*, 1934, 134, 142; *Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1934, 116, 1416; *ibid.*, 1935, 118, 56) indicated that young infants upto an age of 5 months are capable of synthesising vitamin C. The conclusion was drawn that the embryo was able to synthesise vitamin C and that in the case of human subjects, this ability persisted for a short time after birth. Lately, Rohmer, Bezssonoff and Stoerr (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 121, 987) found a higher concentration of vitamin C in the cerebrospinal fluid of prematurely born infants than in that of normal infants, which they considered to lend support to their argument that the foetus synthesises vitamin C. This view is not supported by Mouriquand *et al* (*Compt. rend. Soc. Biol.*, 1936, 121, 1005). Inconclusive results were obtained by Giroud *et al* (*ibid.*, 1936, 121, 1061). Laporta and Renaldi (*Bull. soc. Ital. sper.*, 1936, 11, 141) do not support the view that corpus luteum or the foetus can synthesise vitamin C.

In view of these contradictory results the present experiments were carried out and the behaviour of pregnant guinea-pigs and also of guinea-pigs injected with antuitrin-S on a scorbutic diet was investigated approximately by the method of Bourne. Further, the action of luteinising hormone (antuitrin-S) and of the follicular hormone (theelin) on the concentration of vitamin C in different organs like liver, kidney, spleen, small intestine and adrenal glands of female guinea-pigs has been investigated in order to explore whether these powerful sex-hormones have any relation to the synthesis of vitamin C in the body. The question seemed worthy of

study as a possible relation between vitamin C and sex hormones is indicated by the work of Bourne and some other investigators and also by the fact that the corpus luteum and the anterior pituitary body are relatively very rich in vitamin C.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Three sets of female guinea-pigs were kept on a scorbutic diet consisting of powdered gram (20 parts) and oats (80 parts), cod liver oil, salt and milk autoclaved for half an hour at 12 lb pressure. The three sets of animals consist of:—(1) virgin guinea-pigs kept as controls; (2) virgin guinea-pigs injected subcutaneously with 50 rat units (0.5 c.c) of antuitrin-S (Parke Davis & Co) daily till they died; (3) pregnant guinea-pigs.

TABLE I.

No.	Body weight.	Date of beginning the expt.	Date of death.	Period of survival on scorbutic diet.
A. Controls.				
1	230 g.	11-11-37	9-12-37	28 days.
2	200	"	8-12-37	27
3	215	"	24-12-37	43
4	210	"	24-12-37	43
5	220	"	"	43
B. Treated with antuitrin-S.				
1	205	"	22-12-37	41
2	180	"	21-12-37	40
3	190	"	22-12-37	41
4	170	"	2-12-37	21
5	250	"	3-12-37.	22
C. Pregnant.				
1	300	"	7-12-37	26
2	260	"	Survived*	...
3	260	"	20-12-37	39
4	230	"	Survived* died on 29-12-37.	...
5	335	"	Survived*	...
6	325	"	7-12-37	26
7	280	"	Survived*	...
8	285	"	24-12-37	43

* Survived after 24-12-38, when all the controls died.

Another two sets, one consisting of virgin female guinea-pigs and the other consisting of pregnant guinea-pigs in their advanced stage of pregnancy were experimented on.

TABLE II.

A. Pregnant.

No.	Body weight.	Date of beginning the expt.	Date of death.	Period of survival on scorbutic diet.
1	422 g.	2-2-38	4-3-38	30 days.
2	447	"	15-3-38	30
3	457	"	23-3-38	49
4	370	"	28-3-38	44
5	380	"	27-3-38	53

B. Controls.

1	260	2-2-38	12-3-38	40
2	270	"	7-3-38	35
3	240	"	20-3-38	48
4	250	"	20-3-38	48

Effect of Antuitrin-S and Theelin on Vitamin C Concentration in the Organs of Normal Female Guinea-pigs.

Three sets of female virgin guinea-pigs were taken, of which one set of 6 animals was injected every day with 0.5 c.c. (50 rat units) of antuitrin S. The second set of 6 animals was treated with 0.25 c.c. (50 international units) of theelin, while the third set of animals was kept as control. For seven days the subcutaneous injection of antuitrin-S and theelin were continued. On the eighth day each animal was killed by a blow on the head and in different organs the vitamin C values were estimated by the usual titrimetric technique with 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (Ghosh and Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935 12, 30).

TABLE III.

A. Theelin (50 international units).

No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per			
		10 g. of liver.	3 g. of kidney.	1 g. of spleen	5 g. of adrenal +small intestine.
1	285 g.	0.65	0.12	0.340	0.33
2	240	0.64	0.14	0.265	0.31
3	255	0.68	0.18	0.220	0.27
4	190	0.80	0.27	0.380	0.28
5	225	0.88	0.11	0.230	0.19
6	200	0.90	0.22	0.325	0.40
	Average	0.76	0.17	0.29	0.30

B. Antuitrin-S (50 rat units).

1	200	0.90	0.20	0.320	0.13
2	280	0.70	0.13	0.276	0.22
3	255	0.80	0.18	0.216	0.31
4	235	0.93	0.23	0.360	0.23
5	250	0.87	0.17	0.200	0.19
6	170	0.85	0.14	0.206	0.28
	Average	0.84	0.18	0.263	0.23

C. Control.

1	240	0.94	0.23	0.265	0.38
2	265	0.95	0.18	0.180	0.30
3	225	0.91	0.18	0.172	0.30
4	245	0.96	0.17	0.300	0.22
5	195	0.63	0.17	0.345	0.22
6	195	0.93	0.16	0.310	0.34
	Average	0.89	0.18	0.262	0.29

Statistical Note.

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It is clear from Table I that antuitrin-S has failed to produce any improvement. The animals in the control group lived for 32.8 days on an average, while the corresponding average life of those treated with antuitrin-S was 33 days.

If we take the period between 11-11-37 and 24-12-37 as the period of experiment and compare the pregnant group with the control group we get the following data.

	Died.	Survived.	Total.
Control	... 5	...	5
Pregnant	... 4	4	8
Total	... 9	4	13

The probability of such an event arising out of chance alone is given by

$$P = \frac{.28}{.143} = 19.6\%.$$

With such high probability for chance occurrence we are to conclude that pregnancy does not make any significant difference,

In the second set of experiments (Table II) the behaviour of the pregnant animals is probably inferior to that of the controls. The average lives of the pregnant and the control animals are 28.6 days and 40.8 days respectively.

The mean ascorbic acid contents in liver, kidney, spleen and small intestine in each of the three sets of experiments, as calculated from Table III, are shown in the following table :—

Mean Ascorbic Acid in mg.

Expt.	Liver (per 10 g.).	Kidney (per 3 g.).	Spleen (per g.).	Small intestine (per 5 g.).
A	0.76	0.17	0.29	0.30
B	0.84	0.18	0.26	0.23
C	0.89	0.18	0.26	0.29

The following analyses of variance have been worked out to test the significance of the differences of the means in the three experiments,

Analysis of variance.

	Source of variation.	Degree of freedom.	Sum of square.	Mean square.
Liver	Between expt.	2	0.0545	0.0273
	Within expt.	15	0.1852	0.0123
	Total	17	0.2407	
Kidney	Between expt.	2	0.0002	0.0001
	Within expt.	15	0.0296	0.0020
Spleen	Between expt.	2	0.0038	0.0019
	Within expt.	15	0.0686	0.0046
	Total	17	0.0724	
Small intestine	Between expt.	2	0.0187	0.0094
	Within expt.	15	0.0654	0.0004
	Total	17	0.0841	

In two cases the mean square between experiments, is greater than that within experiments, but the ratio is not significant. Hence injections of autuitrin-S and theelin has not given results significantly different from those produced in the control group.

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